

Harmonization of Advanced Materials Ecosystems serving strategic Innovation Markets to pave the way to a Digital Materials & Product Passport

HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-39

Coordination and knowledge sharing across materials development communities (CSA)

Grant Agreement No 101138510

Start Date of the Project: 01/04/2024

Duration: 36 months

White Paper

Relation of DigiPass CSA and call topic HORIZON-CL4-INDUSTRY-2025-01-MATERIALS-45 Materials Commons for Europe (IA)

April 20, 2026

TABLE OF CONTENT

- 1. PREAMBLE 1
- 2. TIMELINE EXPECTATIONS FROM THE MATERIALS COMMONS CALL TEXT AND MAPPING TO DIGIPASS PROGRESS..... 1
- 3. RELATION OF DIGIPASS-CSA AND THE MATERIALS COMMONS CALL TOPIC 2
 - 3.1 Phase 1 of Materials Commons: Planning and Framework Establishment 2
 - 3.2 Phase 2 and Phase 3 of Materials Commons: Initial build-up and Demonstration 3
- 4. RELATION OF THE DIGIPASS CONTINUATION AND THE MATERIALS COMMONS CALL TOPIC..... 3

Funded by the European Union

DigiPass project has been funded by the European Commission for the programme HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01, Grant Agreement No 101138510
WIKKI LIMITED, UK participant in Horizon Europe Project DigiPass, is supported by UKRI grant number 10100819: DigiPass

1. Preamble

The overarching objective of DigiPass-CSA (call topic HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-39, Grant Agreement No 101138510) is to enhance the digital maturity of the European communities that develop materials and intermediate products. The project develops recommendations and clear routes toward digitalized circular business models. The overarching key result of DigiPass is to create a sustainable platform which includes support for Digital Materials & Product Passport and for collaborative, SSbD-driven innovation-by-design processes in a circular economy served by Advanced Materials (AM). The interoperability and FAIRness of the materials data and ensuring a connection of the DigiPass platform with the Materials Commons federated infrastructure are the common goal of the demonstration platform development.

2. Timeline expectations from the Materials Commons call text and mapping to DigiPass progress

Mai 2027: The technical development of the DigiPass-CSA project ends, and DigiPass-CSA expects that the project under the Materials Commons call topic will have concluded its **Phase 1**, meaning that the planning of the Materials Commons infrastructure is completed. The public DigiPass-CSA deliverables are basically related to the planning phase of the Materials Commons project. In contrast to Materials Commons, DigiPass-CSA is not an infrastructure project. It implements a TRL5-6 digital platform to integrate digitalisation aspects of the value chains through demonstrator cases. Nevertheless, relations between DigiPass-CSA and the Materials Commons Phase-1 (planning) are readily identified below.

Relations between **Phase 2** and **Phase 3** of the Materials Commons project and the DigiPass-CSA are informative only since DigiPass-CSA is completed once Phase-2 and Phase-3 of Materials Commons will start. Those relations are basically restricted to the area of semantic interoperability, to User Story-based governance model implementation, and to a structured approach to onboarding new stakeholders on digital platforms/ infrastructures.

However, DigiPass-CSA has the ambition to form a legal entity to ensure sustainability of the project results. Under the assumption that the business model, to be constructed, includes the aspects given below, relations to Phase-2 and Phase-3 can be envisioned.

3. Relation of DigiPass-CSA and the Materials Commons call topic

3.1 Phase 1 of Materials Commons: Planning and Framework Establishment

Materials Commons	Selected DigiPass results	Relation and Cooperation potential
<p>Developing functional and non-functional requirements and identifying existing solutions (e.g., cloud solutions, middleware, data spaces) that can be used to accelerate or be integrated into the infrastructure. Identification of possible use of existing infrastructures and resources, including support for and integration of self-driving labs.</p>	<p>Functional and non-functional requirements for hosting DPPs along value chains, seamless transfer from digitalised open innovation processes to daisy-chained DPPs.</p>	<p>Identification of User Groups (roles according to the ESPR) and their User Stories as a basis for requirements engineering.</p>
<p>Planning a governance framework, able to implement the infrastructure meeting the functional and non-functional requirements, including a strategy for adhesion of new entities in the long term.</p>	<p>Requirements engineering based on User Stories and other (regulatory) requirements (GDPR, SSbD framework, etc.)</p>	<p>The governance framework in DigiPass related to the DigiPass User Stories is essentially determined by regulation (ESPR).</p>
<p>Agreeing on long-term sustainability plan, taking into account academic, industry needs and aspects going beyond R&I.</p>	<p>DigiPass business model and legal entity formation.</p>	<p>CAPEX- and OPEX-planning for nodes and for a governing body of a federated digital infrastructure.</p>
<p>Determining compatibility issues and standardisation needs, also in relation to semantic interoperability.</p>	<p>Regulatory-compliant DPPs, including interlinked DPPs and data sharing along value chains. Overview and recommendations on Technology available for interoperable data exchange.</p>	<p>Interoperability approaches on digital platforms for specific domains.</p>

Setting out key stakeholders, including from academia and industry and related projects and initiatives which will be the users of the infrastructure.	Industrial stakeholders are aligned along value chains with the objective to provide interlinked DPPs and share (materials) data.	Open innovation processes (including issues related to SSbD). Communities interested in materials digitalisation on federated infrastructures.
--	---	--

3.2 Phase 2 and Phase 3 of Materials Commons: Initial build-up and Demonstration

These phases are expected to start after DigiPass-CSA concludes, thus DigiPass-CSA results may serve as information source only. DigiPass-CSA consortium members are active in IAM4EU and will use the DigiPass results in IAM4EU and Materials Commons project cooperations. However, not all aspects covered in Phase 2 and Phase 3 are directly related to DigiPass-CSA and the next table discuss exclusively those topics where DigiPass-CSA results may play a role in Materials Commons.

Materials Commons	DigiPass-CSA results	Potentially valuable DigiPass-CSA information
Governance framework for data, computational tools and workflows at the operational level	Daisy-chained DPPs and role-based DPP information access are intertwined, e.g. information on supply chains is visible only to the extent necessary for fulfilling an (ESPR-) role.	Implementation architecture of governance model of non-technological information in daisy-chained data sets (for Materials Commons: from raw/recycled material to material produced, e.g. steel).
5 use cases across different sectors and related demonstrators	DigiPass-CSA demonstration of daisy-chained DPPs, results of Open Call.	DigiPass on-boarding mechanism for new actors in a value chain.
Concrete steps towards sustainability	DigiPass-CSA business model	Requirements on a sustainable infrastructure for running materials digitalization.

4. Relation of the DigiPass continuation and the Materials Commons call topic

The continuation of DigiPass will run under a business model which by itself is a result of the DigiPass-CSA. This model is still under debate, so the elements discussed below are to be considered with reservation that they are going to be part of the business model.

However, it is undisputed in the DigiPass-CSA consortium that the business model will not include running digital infrastructure nodes/servers; the continuation of DigiPass-CSA will establish a

service-oriented business model. Therefore, not all aspects of the Materials Commons **Phase 2** and **Phase 3** are considered.

Materials Commons	DigiPass legal entity	Relation and Cooperation potential
Governance framework for data, computational tools and workflows at operational level.	Integration of (Open-) Innovation digitalization, seamless transition to DPP and corresponding Governance framework	Data security measures, mixed open-closed digital objects in one workflow.
Standards and machine readable, domain-specific data schemas and Advanced Programming Interfaces, enabling semantic interoperability and interconnections between different datasets and tools	Interoperable DPP system, including daisy chained DPPs with highly fine-tuned role-based access rights.	Integration of domain specific digital objects in cross-enabled innovation processes targeting production.
Support for European self-driving labs and their interconnection to the infrastructure, enabling them to reach higher levels of data-driven decision making and automated workflows.	DigiPass aims to connect SSbD, OIP, OITB, and Technology Infrastructures frameworks at a data level and business model level.	Materials Commons digital infrastructure could be federated in DigiPass existing ecosystem.
Integration of workflows and tools, including those aimed at creation of primary data.	DigiPass platform is workflow based using a business standard.	Integration of services in workflow engines as a new level of interoperability.
5 use cases across different sectors and related demonstrators, facilitating industrial uptake and offering a feedback loop to academic research.	Use Cases are business cases. Simplification and seamless access for SMEs.	Management of “customer relationships”. DigiPass may serve as a single-entry point (SEP) for SMEs.
Concrete steps towards sustainability.	DigiPass operates under a service-oriented and sustainable business model	Materials Commons infrastructure may serve as backend for the DigiPass exploitation strategy & business model.

Authors	Natalia Konchakova (Hereon) Peter Klein (Fraunhofer ITWM) Franz Pirker (AC2T) Heinz A. Preisig (NTNU) Salim Belouettar (LIST)
Contributors	DigiPass Consortium members